

THE PERCEPTION OF COMMUNICATIVE LANGUAGE TEACHING METHOD IN EDUCATION

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Annotation: In today's rapidly changing world the great improvements can be mentioned in Education also, especially, it can be seen in the sphere of teaching foreign languages. Communicative language teaching method has already become a vital part of English teaching methodology and it is still widely used by foreign language teachers. Besides, the topic of communicative language teaching is in the centre of attention and investigation of linguists.

Key words: communication, communicative language teaching, communicative method, a communicative perspective on language, communicative perspective on learning, "Humanistic" approach, traditional technique, language components, oral and written speech.

In the world of the methodology of teaching English, there are constant debates on what method of learning English is better. Proponents of the classical methodology say that this traditional way of learning a language is more preferable. After all, it involves practicing all four basic language skills: speaking, listening, reading and writing. It also expands lexical vocabulary and improves pronunciation. Supporters of the communicative technique point out the shortcomings of this technique. First, with a comprehensive study of the language, there is no time left for purely conversational practice, and secondly, teachers, as a rule, are not native speakers. Therefore, if the goal of a person is to learn how to communicate, then in this case the communicative method suits him more.

The relevance of this study lies in the differentiation of classical and Communicative methods. This question is relevant due to the fact that in the modern world the method of teaching and learning English and their number is constantly growing. Therefore, a person who wants to learn a language will need to choose a technique or course. Analysis of research and scientific publications shows that the problem of teaching methods attracts the attention of many famous scientists and educators-practitioners. Among them are M.F.Stronin, K.D.Ushinsky, I.M.Melnik, A. O.Toporov, N.P.Anikeeva and others.

One important source of uncertainty about the meaning of Communicative language teaching (CLT) is that from the outset, it has existed in two different versions which correspond roughly to the two main sources of CLT: a communicative perspective on language and a communicative perspective on learning.

The communicative perspective on learning focuses attention on how we learn, especially on our natural capacities to ‘acquire’ language simply through communication without explicit instruction. These ideas were embodied in proposals such as Krashen and Terrell’s [4, P.1-16] “Natural approach”, which was based on the belief that only natural acquisition processes can lead to effective language learning; Prabhu’s [6, P.94] “Communicational Language Teaching”, which insisted that conscious learning and error correction have no place in the language classroom; and “Humanistic” approaches, which emphasized the importance of engaging learners in communication in which their whole personality is invested. In classroom practice, both perspectives lead to an emphasis on ‘communication in the classroom’ Johnson and Morrow. But if we focus only on the communicative perspective on learning, we may draw the conclusion that involvement in communication is sufficient in itself for learning and that we should not make any use at all of “Traditional” techniques such as explanations, drills and question-and-answer practice. This has often been called Howatt, [3, 287 p.] the “Strong’ version of CLT”. The communicative perspective on language, on the other hand, still leaves open the possibility that teachers might present and practice individual items (in a communicative context) before or after students use them for communication. This has often been called again after Howatt, [3, 287 p.] the “Weak version of CLT”. The two versions of CLT have different implications for how language is best learnt in the classroom and for the role of the teacher. Both versions require the teacher to be a creator and organizer of communicative activities, which presents challenging roles for teachers and learners, but the weak version, adopts a more familiar overall framework through its recognition of controlled and analytic learning. Allwright and Hanks [1, P.47-49] argue that the ‘much less challenging ideas’ of this weak version (Littlewood), [5, P.76].

In today's world, things are changing rapidly. The methods of learning English are also changing. More and more education centers use video materials, multimedia, role-playing games in their work. It is believed that the study of language will be effective only if the person receives pleasure from the process itself, and does not motivate itself only by the fact that the study of language is a necessity. The main purpose of learning English is not only the formation and development of the

communicative culture of people who learn the language, but also their training in the practical acquisition of English. Now language teaching has become more applied, while earlier it was more theoretical in nature. The role of the teacher has changed. Dictator - the teacher is not able to provide students with the freedom of choice, which is necessary in the process of learning English. The teacher-intermediary, the teacher-observer, simply the head came to replace this teacher. Although the role of the teacher in this case is not the main one, his influence on the audience, which, in turn, becomes more intimate, does not diminish, but, on the contrary, increases. It is the teacher who is the organizer of group interaction that encourages students to communicate with each other with maximum effect, interest and benefit. In the classroom, students are no longer limited in their choice of language means and speech behavior. The teacher also has the opportunity to choose any methods and techniques of training - role-playing, training, and exercises. Now, more than ever, an English teacher has the ability to select any textbooks, as well as the ability to create, combine and modify the material based on the needs of students. Therefore, in modern conditions, the role of the teacher is changing. Now the English teacher is increasingly acting as a partner and consultant. He no longer focuses on the study of outdated topics; themes are determined by the reality of the events that their participants are experiencing [2, P.22]. The development of a lesson plan is carried out together with its participants during the lesson, and not in advance. If the participants are not interested in learning by heart materials from the history of Great Britain, as well as studying texts on the most important events in the history of this country, the modern teacher will not be forced to do so. What is important is not the teacher and his materials, but the participants in the lesson, developing their potential, searching for opportunities to correct mistakes. Modern methods of learning English offer freedom of choice. If a person is interested in football, cinema or art, then why not study these topics? After all, each person seeks to accumulate knowledge and experience that are important for him. Of course, different people learn English. Therefore, if it is much more interesting for someone to discuss sports and cinema, and not Buckingham Palace and kings with queens, then for the teacher the topics suggested by the students should be more important than the outdated topics of textbooks.

The approach to teaching English has changed a lot. Previously, priority was given to the classical or, as it is otherwise called, the fundamental method of teaching English. The tasks used in this technique are quite uniform - reading the text, translation and exercises in the text. When studying topics, only one language function is implemented - informative. The classical approach is based on the understanding of

the language as a real and complete means of communication, which means that all language components - oral and written speech, listening, etc. should be developed in students systematically and harmoniously. Such an integrated approach is aimed at developing students' ability to understand and create speech, compare two language systems and learn grammatical rules. A teacher who uses modern methods of teaching English should try to help his students to show their individuality and develop independence of thought. Modern methods of learning English also offer a creative approach to learning: poetry, sayings, films and sports broadcasts. You can turn on the tape recorder and listen to the song, and then try to make out the words of the song and translate them into Ukrainian. This task is interesting, it does not make the students bored, especially when there are a lot of tasks and they are changing rapidly. So, there are a lot of tools for the formation of students' communicative competence. After all, the formation of communicative competence and is the main purpose of learning a foreign language, the rest - educational, educational, developing are implemented in the process of implementing this main goal. The communicative approach includes the formation of communication skills and intercultural interaction skills.

Thus, we can conclude that the use of the communicative method in teaching English to foreign students in intensive language courses in the UK has its advantages over the traditional method thanks to active forms of education, one of which is role-playing. Students studying this method can creatively use their knowledge, quickly and effectively learn English and acquire language practice.

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